

DELIVERABLE

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Report on integration of cryo-blades and cryo-imaging into the Titan-Holo microscope at FZJ (release 1)

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The purpose of this deliverable is to explain the unique design of cryo-blades with respect to the possibilities and restriction of the electron microscope dedicated to QSORT project for cryo-Em experiments as explained in WP5. In particular this deliverable describes the features that should have been considered to implement novel cryo-blades in a TITAN electron microscope.

The long-term objective is to determine the best possible configuration of a set of retractable cryoblades in the TITAN HOLO microscope protecting a frozen biological specimen (cooled to liquid nitrogen temperature) to be safely studied with no contamination effect from the residual organic contaminants inside the electron microscope column and allowing also to implement Sorter phase element for the actual experiments since the microscope must be operated in non-standard conditions.

The principal challenge of this implementation is the possibility to adapt a machine normally suited for material science and in particular holography to perform cryomicroscopy without losing the performances in material science. This makes the machine an “unicum” in the electron microscopy landscape. Moreover, the new elements for QSORT like the special MEMS aperture has been considered as a constraint for the realization of the project.

This deliverable complies with the Q-SORT description of work outlined in *Work Package 5, task 5.1 Integration of cryo-elements in the TEM at FZJ*.

The deliverable has been produced thanks to confidential information about the microscope column, previous designs of commercially existing cryo-blades, engineering drawings of internal ports TEM octagon provided by the support of the partner FEI.

It is intended to benefit directly the work of the following interrelated tasks:

- *Task 5.2 Spiral phase plate test.*
- *Task 5.3 Experimental application of the sorter to protein orientation problem.*
- *Task 5.4 Minimally destructive wave recognition of proteins*

In passing the possibility to still use the microscope for material science is necessary for the development of WP4.

The current document is comprised of three main Chapters, an Executive Summary and Conclusions. The first chapter introduces the essence of cryo-blades for cryo-EM experiments on biological sample, its features and possibilities.

The second chapter describes the limitations of the existing electron microscope, i.e. TITAN HOLO to install a commercially available cryo-box or even cryo-blades in the specimen area.

The third chapter discusses the novel design of cryo-blades to be installed in TITAN HOLL, specially done for the QSORT project.

1. CRYO-BLADES FOR CRYO-EM

1.1 Cryo-EM

The imaging of frozen hydrated samples by cryo-TEM is nowadays used to characterize a wide variety of structures. This technique improves the results obtained by standard imaging in some cases where the classical methods are difficult to use. Moreover, there is a whole class of structures that cannot be visualized in dry specimens because they only exist under the action of forces which are acting in liquid water. Examples of structures that have been characterized with this technique include viruses, ribosomes, actin filaments, several kinds of **proteins** and other macromolecules as lipid and lipid vesicles.

Characterization of frozen hydrated samples by cryo-TEM requires several specialized steps from sample preparation to visualization

Cryo-immobilization of sample containing solution by plunge freezing. Vitrobot Mark IV is the tool we have selected for this purpose. 3 μ l of the solution is deposited in a Quantifoil or C-flat grid in a temperature and humidity-controlled chamber. After a blotting process the sample is plunged into liquid ethane close to its solidification temperature.

Transfer of sample to cryo-holder: the holder must be previously prepared to ensure isolation of its dewar and cooling transmission from liquid nitrogen to the sample in its tip. Several hours of holder evacuation in the turbo-pumping station and zeolite cycle with the cold stage controller are required. Sample transfer is performed under liquid nitrogen in the cryo workstation

The holder is introduced in the microscope and visualized under the cryo-protection of cryo-blades and using Low Dose mode.

1.2 Cryo-Box (Cryo-Blades)

The idea of cryo microscopy is to get the organic compounds inside the microscope through a cold driven diffusion. There are different implementations depending on the geometry of the cold elements. These can be in the form of 2 metallic blades on top and below the specimen (cryoblades) or in the form of a nearly complete box surrounding the specimen in all directions (cryobox).

The main problem with cryoblades and boxes is the typical size of the object that should fit within the polar expansion of the objective lens.

The cryoblades are retractable or, more often, fixed and substitute the normal cold trap that is used in conventional microscopy as cryo getter.

The objective lens region of the microscope where the specimen is hosted has 8 flanges that permit the access to the specimen region.

The conundrum of this deliverable is that we need to find the space for hosting retractable cryoblades compatible with the rest of the column. Moreover, we have a smaller dimension in the Z direction with respect to standard

2 RESTRICTIONS OF THE TITAN HOLO MICROSCOPE

2.1 Current configuration of TITAN HOLO's octagon

As explained in section 1.2, the commercial cryo-box or cryo-blade should be installed on the port number "5". However, this port has to be dedicated to an UHV transfer system, ideated and built for different purposes than the QSORT project and hence, a newly designed cryo-blades should be fabricated to be installed on another port.

Fig 1. Scheme of current configuration of TTAN HOLO's Octagon

2.2 Implementation of the MEMS aperture holder element

One of the most important restriction that makes the standard cryo-blades very difficult to be installed on TITAN HOLO microscope resulted from the installation of the First Sorter phase element in the objective aperture position, port "3". A new MEMS aperture holder has been designed and is fabricated

to implement this element in appropriate position, see fig 2. This aperture is much thicker than standard objective aperture due to electrical contact and MEMS chip of the phase element which may interfere with the standard cryo-box or cryo-blade.

Fig 2. MEMS aperture holder for Sorter phase element (a) MEMS mounting mechanism, (b) overall configuration of the MEMS aperture inside the microscope column.

Hence, the new cryo-blades should be designed and installed on octagon matching the configuration shown in figure 3.

Fig 3. Scheme of TTAN HOLO's Octagon configuration for new cryo-blades.

3 CRYO-BLADES FOR TITAN HOLO

According to the mentioned limitations in section 2, a novel cryo-blade system has been designed for QSORT project considering possible different solutions which may result during the cryo-experiments and also other experiments within the project.

3.1 General Requests

- For the ER-C lab's Titan "Holo" a cryo sample protection device is requested.
- The aimed use is to protect a cryo sample which is inserted via a side entry cryoholder.
- For non-cryo samples it must be possible to remove the protection shield out of the e-beam.
- During non-cryo use the cold trap function of the cooled parts must be sufficient to do normal TEM – work.
- The solution can be completely manual, no SW control is needed.
- The solution shall not mechanically interfere with other parts or options in and on the octagon.

- The covers may be removed from the Titan Holo where needed.
- The actual dimensions of the holes in the cryo shield will be agreed upon with FEI.
- The pole-hit detection must remain intact with the chosen solution.
- The solution must be x-ray safe at 300 kV.

3.2 Microscope specification

- FEI Titan G2 60-300 Low Base
- XFEG
- CTWIN pole pieces (11 mm gap)
- Special Krios Obj. aperture holder with sliding alignment plates
- Image Corrector
- 2x Faraday cups
- Lorentz lens

3.2.1 Microscope upgrades within and out of QSORT project

- MEMS Obj. Aperture holder, via Thermo Fisher NSR
- Additional Non Thermo Fisher items:
 - Vacuum Sample Transfer system, opposite of Compustage
 - Light option via port between obj. aperture and Compustage

3.3 Octagon configuration with novel cryo-blade

Hence, it has been decided to mount the cryo-blades at 90° to the specimen holder. These blades would be retractable, i.e. can be parked far from optical axis of the microscope as shown in figure 4 and can be easily inserted into center of optical axis as shown in figure 5. The blades are connected by a socket to the cool finger connected to the dewar of liquid nitrogen

Fig 4. Scheme of TTAN HOLO's Octagon configuration with new cryo-blades in park position.

Fig 5. Scheme of TTAN HOLO's Octagon configuration with new cryo-blades inserted.

These blades will shield water molecules coming from the liner tubes and the octagon quite effectively. Also, as shown in figure 6, Symmetric cryo-blades are preferred because tilt is limited by the blade closest to the holder. However, the whole system is asymmetric. On top of the blades we allow for an extra element for light induction experiment not connected with the QSORT project. Enough space is also foreseen between the retractable cryo-blades and the MEMS aperture holder to reduce the possibility of mechanical obstruction and contact.

Since the new cold finger is in contact with large parts of the column the consumption of liquid nitrogen is larger, a new large volume LN2 dewar is therefore foreseen to be mounted on microscope column allowing long stand time operation, e.g. > 8 hrs.

Fig 6. Scheme of TITAN HOLO's Octagon configuration with new cryo-blades inserted, side view.

In order to install such cryo-blades in the octagon of TITAN HOLO from these special ports the original cold-trap of the microscope should be removed to providing enough space at the port 7 and 8. This means the microscope column should be split: the upper pole-piece should be brought out and the cold trap should be completely removed from the column. Hence, the installation of the cryo-blades will be considered as a permanent modification for TITAN HOLO.

While inserted cryoblades do normally ensure a strong cryo protection from contaminant, in the non-inserted mode the cryoblades system is potentially a less efficient getter for contaminants with respect to the traditional cold finger. The reason lies in the geometry of the cold trap that in traditional technology surrounds the specimen region while here a single side is exposed to liquid nitrogen.

Still according to expert evaluation this should not be a limiting factor.

3.4 Novel cryo-blade design

It has been decided to employ the existing shape of the blades, previously used in FEI-Tecnai microscopes, as shown in figure 7. However, all dimensions should be calculated from the beginning to be optimized for TITAN HOLO column. It is can be seen in figure 7, two sets of holes can be used on the blades with different holes size for different application, i.e. various biological specimens.

Figure 8 shows the final configuration of the cryo-blades, Sorter phase element and specimen holder in the octagon from top view as it should work during QSORT experiments.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this deliverable we demonstrated the efforts to produce a dedicated design for a cryo-blades system to be installed in TITAN HOLO microscope enabling to conduct cryo-microscopy experiment on biological specimen within QSORT project and still retain the compatibility with the day by day material science use of the microscope.

The cryoblades to be introduced in the microscopes are highly nonstandard and required a complete redesign by FEI engineer and the specific fabrication out of the normal processing chain.

The main restriction we considered are in the possibility to retract the cryoblades, in the reduced dimension and in the compatibility with the MEMS holder and other elements in the TITAN HOLO.

The splitting of the column is, by itself a delicate operation that requires a complete stop of the microscope operation and a realignment procedure. Finally, the anticontamination effect when the cryoblades are retracted have been also considered.

In spite of the difficulty having this multipurpose microscope like this will be already an interesting outcome of the project.

ANNEX 1: REFEREE

Vincenzo Grillo (CNR):

This deliverable is accurate and interesting. The author highlights the many challenges in this new configuration. I am very happy that the new instrument will be unique in the FEI instrumentation landscape.

I have a few minor questions- It seem that the special cryobox you are building is smaller than usual cryo-boxes. What is the drawback of this special configuration?

- Titan Holo is the same microscope that we will use for material science operations in this project.

Is the splitting of the column going to affect any deliverable in this project?

Answer

We appreciate your comments. Clearly your feedback is the most valuable in this project.

The contribution of FEI inside the project is essential in this development. It allows me also to answer to your questions.

- Yes, the smaller cryo-boxes will impose a limitation on specimen tilt and therefore on single particle tomography.

Nevertheless, this is not of direct interest in the project.

- No, we will book the microscope time ahead of the splitting in order to finish all experimental operations on time.

Giancarlo Gazzadi (CNR):

The report describes the integration of Cryo-blades into a Titan-Holo transmission electron microscope. It starts with the scientific motivation of such an implementation, and then analyses in detail the critical technical issues that have to be faced. The proposed solution, i.e. to adopt a cryo-blades' design similar to the one used in other FEI microscopes, with the proper scaling of dimensions in order to fit into the TITAN-Holo microscope, seems to meet successfully the requirements of the cryo-measurements preserving the existing functionalities of the microscope.

ANNEX 2: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
National Research Council (Project scientific coordinator)	Italy	CNR
Forschungszentrum Jülich, Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons	Germany	FZJ
FEI - Thermo Fisher Scientific	The Netherlands	FEI
The Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light	Germany	MPI
University of Glasgow, Department of Physics and Astronomy	United Kingdom	UG
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd. - UK	United Kingdom	QED
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Department of Physics, Informatics, and Mathematics - IT	Italy	UMR
Maastricht University, Multi Modal Molecular Imaging Institute	The Netherlands	MU

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL